

drops) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr after which the solvent and excess thionyl chloride were removed *in vacuo*. The crude acid chloride was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide (200 ml) and cooled to 0°. Stannic chloride (12.1 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring and the mixture was allowed to come to room temperature and stirred for another 2.5 hr. After hydrolysis with ice and hydrochloric acid, the organic layer was separated, washed with dil. HCl, water, sodium bicarbonate solution, and then again with water and finally dried and distilled to give the cyclohepta[b]thiophenone (7) which slowly solidified, b.p. 165°/1 mm, pale yellow solid, m.p. 65° (8 g, 62%). λ_{\max} 256 (log ϵ 3.85); ν_{\max} (KBr): 1660 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 1.75 (2H, t), 2.55 (2H, s), 2.9 (2H, t), 7.0 (1H, d) and 7.3 ppm (1H, d). 2,4-DNP derivative of 7 was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. 178-180°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (10): The ketone (7) (5.46 g; 0.023 mole) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure, as described earlier using diethylene glycol (28 ml), potassium hydroxide (4.5 g) and ~99% hydrazine hydrate (5.5 ml). After usual work-up the reduced product (10) distilled at 122°/0.4 mm (4.95 g, 96.4%).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-methyl-2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (2): Prepared as described for the keto acid (1) from 2-methylthiophen and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride in 86% yield, m.p. 100° (from benzene-light petroleum), ν_{\max} (KBr): 1640 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 2.4 (3H, s), 2.5 (2H, s), 3.0 (2H, s), 6.7 (1H, d), 7.5 (1H, d) and 11.0 ppm (1H, s).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-methyl-2-thienyl)pentanoic acid (5): Prepared by Huang-Minlon reduction of 2 by the method described earlier in 83% yield. The acid (5) had b.p. 186°/1.1 mm. It slowly solidified on cooling, m.p. 52°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (8): The reduced acid (5) was converted to the acid chloride by thionyl chloride method and finally cyclised to the cyclic ketone (8) by stannic chloride in 80.7% yield. It had b.p. 155°/0.8 mm and slowly solidified on cooling, m.p. 90°. λ_{\max} 257 (log ϵ 4.0); ν_{\max} (KBr): 1655 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 1.75 (2H, t), 2.3 (3H, s), 2.55 (2H, s), 2.9 (2H, t) and 6.95 ppm (1H, s). 2,4-DNP derivative of 8 was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. 227°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (11): The cyclic ketone (8) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to give the spiran (11) in 93% yield, b.p. 145°/1.2 mm.

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-ethyl-2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (3): Prepared from 2-ethylthiophen and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride in 90% yield. The keto acid (3) crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 88°; ν_{\max} (KBr): 1640 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.2 (3H, t),

1.4 (10H, s), 2.75 (2H, s), 2.8 (2H, m), 3.0 (2H, s), 6.8 (1H, d), 7.55 (1H, d) and 11.0 ppm (1H, s).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-ethyl-2-thienyl)pentanoic acid (6): Reduction of the keto acid (3) by Huang-Minlon procedure gave the reduced acid (6) in 82% yield, b.p. 195°/1.2 mm.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (9): The reduced acid (6) was converted to the acid chloride by thionyl chloride method and finally cyclised to the cyclic ketone (9) by stannic chloride in 80% yield, b.p. 165°/0.8 mm. λ_{\max} 258 (log ϵ 3.9); ν_{\max} (KBr): 1650 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.2 (3H, t), 1.4 (10H, s), 1.75 (2H, t), 2.6 (2H, s), 2.65-2.95 (4H, m) and 7.0 ppm (1H, s). 2,4-DNP derivative of 9 was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 152°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (12): Huang-Minlon reduction of the cyclic ketone (9) gave the spiran (12) in 92% yield, b.p. 158°/1.2 mm.

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Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-2-(2-hydroxy-3'-5'-dichlorophenyl)-3-N-amino-sulphophenyl/4-methyl pyrimidyl/-4, 6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl/3-(N'-2-thiazolylsulphanilamido)-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and their Benzoyl Derivatives

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been found to possess wide variety of physiological properties viz., anticonvulsant¹, sciatic nerve block², spiral anaesthesia², CNS stimulant³, local anaesthetic⁴, analgesic⁵, sedative⁶, choleric⁶ and antiphlogistic⁷.

NOTES

With a view to prepare better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised 2-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-/3',5'-dichlorophenyl)-3,N⁴-sulphonamide-3-methyl pyrimidyl-/3,5-dimethyl pyrimidyl, 3-(N'-2-thiazolyl sulphanyl-amido)/5-H/carboxy methyl-4-thiazolidinones/2'-benzoate by condensing α -phenyl-3,5-dichloro-benzal anils and their benzoyl derivative with thio-

glycollic acid or thiomalic acid. The structures were supported by ir spectra⁹⁻¹² which, in general, showed the ν C=O group frequency at 1640-1655 cm^{-1} , ν N-CO at 1575-1585 cm^{-1} , ν NHSO₂ at 1150-1160 cm^{-1} and ν phenolic OH at 3400-3410 cm^{-1} , (reported ν C=O group frequency at 1655-1760 cm^{-1} , ν N-CO at 1580 cm^{-1} , ν NHSO₂ at 1140-

TABLE 1— α -PHENYL-2-HYDROXY-/3,5-DICHLORO BENZAL ANILS AND THEIR BENZOYL DERIVATIVE

Sl. No.	R	R''	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	H	70	95	6.63 (6.65)	20	—
2.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	75	90	6.10 (5.17)	22	—
3.	4-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	78	105	10.84 (10.89)	24	6
4.	4-Methyl pyrimidyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	68	150	10.81 (8.83)	21	8
5.	4,6-Dimethyl-pyrimidyl	H	63	125	10.56 (10.60)	16	10
6.	4,6-Dimethyl-pyrimidyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	58	196	8.62 (8.64)	16	—
7.	(N'-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamido)	H	55	140	8.89 (8.90)	15	11
8.	(N'-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamido)	C ₆ H ₅ CO	66	165	7.03 (7.07)	20	10

TABLE 2—PREPARATION OF 2-PHENYL-2-(2-HYDROXY)-3',5'-DICHLORO PHENYL-/3-N-AMINOSULPHOPHENYL-4-METHYL PYRIMIDYL-/4,6-DIMETHYL PYRIMIDYL/3-(N'-2-THIAZOLYL SULPHANYLAMIDO)/5-H-/CARBOXYMETHYL-4-THIAZOLIDINONES AND THEIR BENZOYL DERIVATIVE

Sl. No.	R	R'	R''	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm (24 hr)	
							<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	H	H	58	175	5.63 (5.65)	24	4
2.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	60	128	4.64 (4.67)	24	4
3.	4-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	H	75	130	9.50 (9.52)	21	—
4.	4-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	78	105	8.08 (8.09)	20	—
5.	4,6-Dimethyl-pyrimidyl	H	H	68	110	9.28 (9.31)	18	10
6.	4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	56	155	8.17 (8.22)	15	8
7.	(N'-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamido)	H	H	55	133	7.25 (7.26)	22	8
8.	(N'-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamido)	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	69	205	6.24 (6.28)	21	—
9.	H	CH ₃ COOH	H	65	210	5.04 (5.06)	12	—
10.	H	„	C ₆ H ₅ CO	68	180	4.20 (4.27)	12	—
11.	4-Methyl	„	H	70	103	8.62 (8.68)	18	4
12.	4-Methyl	„	C ₆ H ₅ CO	75	163	7.48 (7.47)	9	4
13.	4,6-Dimethyl	„	H	55	171	7.45 (8.50)	17	—
14.	4,6-Dimethyl	„	C ₆ H ₅ CO	58	165	7.80 (7.82)	15	6
15.	(N'-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamido)	„	H	54	202	6.44 (6.47)	16	—
16.	(N'-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamido)	„	C ₆ H ₅ CO	48	130	5.61 (5.68)	18	—

The activity of DMF (control) for *S. aureus* 8 mm and *E. coli* 4 mm.

1160 cm^{-1} , and ν phenolic OH at 3300-3400 cm^{-1}).

where R=H, 4-methyl pyrimidyl, 4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl or (N'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido).

R'=H, CH_3 , COOH

R''=H, COO_2H_3

Experimental

α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3,5-dichloro benzal anils/2-benzoate^{1,3}: 2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichloro benzophenone^{1,4} (0.01 M) dissolved in ethanol, was added to sulphanilamide (0.01 M) in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The contents were poured into water. The product thus isolated was crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated by treatment with benzoylchloride and 10% cold sodium hydroxide solution. The product poured on ice, extracted with solvent ether, and crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

2-Phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro phenyl)-3-N-aminosulphophenyl/4-methyl pyrimidyl/4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl/3(N'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido)-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone and their benzoyl derivative: α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3,5-dichlorobenzal anils/2-benzoate (0.01 M in dry benzene) was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 M) on a water bath for 4 hr. The product thus separated was crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-(2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro phenyl)-3-M-amino sulphophenyl/4-methyl pyrimidyl/4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl/3CN'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido/-5-H/-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and their benzoyl derivative^{1,5}: α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3,5-dichlorobenzal anils (0.01 M) were condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 M) in presence of zinc chloride (0.5 g) for 2 hr at 160° (Reddelien method^{1,6}). The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated by 10% hydrochloric acid, crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Antimicrobial screening: The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate³ method using *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as test organism. The testing was carried out in DMF solution. The difference between the zone of inhibitions of the test solution and pure solvent (DMF) are recored in Tables 1 and 2.

All compounds are highly active against *S. aureus*. In case of anils, where R=H, 4-methyl pyrimidyl and R'=H, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$, the compound possess good activity while in case of 4-thiazolidinones where R=H, N'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido, R'=H and R''=H, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$ the compounds possess good activity.

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Synthesis of 10-Arylidene Anthrones

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THOUGH a lot of work has been reported on anthrone, not much attention has been given to its reactive methylene group. 10-Arylidene anthrones were synthesised by reacting the corresponding 10-anthranyl triphenyl phosphonium, or arsonium yelides with aryl aldehydes¹. Only one direct synthesis of *m*-nitrobenzylidene anthrone was reported² by condensing anthrone with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in piperidine and pyridine base using xylene as a solvent.

It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the reactivity of methylene group. Two methods were followed in the condensation reactions. In one, anthrone was condensed with aryl aldehyde in the presence of acetic anhydride containing a few drops of piperidine base and in the other, alcohol was used as a solvent with a few drops of piperidine base.

Experimental

The m.p.s were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The structures are supported by elemental analysis and spectral data. UV spectra